

Classification of beach user trajectories using stationary Marine Radar

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Summary

Monitoring the coastline using remote sensing technologies has become a fundamental method in underpinning coastal management. Monitoring beach use in a spatio-temporal context provides coastal stakeholders with a breadth of knowledge on the areas of the beach that are important to users and may assist in the implementation of coastal defences and beach resilience measures. This paper provides a novel technique that utilises radar imagery in the tracking, feature extraction and subsequent classification of human beach users. Comparing the accuracy of several classification models, detected particle trajectories are classified into human and non-human and tracked over time. The resulting outputs enable beach user density to be quantified over various spatial and temporal scales.

KEYWORDS – Random Forest, Radar, Trajectories, beach, classification.

1 Introduction

Coastal monitoring strategies have played a fundamental role in beach management. The way in which the beach is used by stakeholders is an important factor in socio-economic beach management. In Europe alone, the tourism industry accounts for over one third of the maritime economy, as well as being a significant contributor to employment within many European countries (European Commission, 2014). Furthermore, anthropogenic stressors have been linked to considerable damage and disturbance to beach ecosystems, affecting many species native to these environments (Soto et al., 2021). As a result, it is within the interests of Coastal managers to feature the social characteristics of beaches in their monitoring strategies.

Beach monitoring has been revolutionised by the field of remote sensing (Bell, Bird and Plater, 2016; Bird et al., 2017). Radar circumvents the limitations posed by other remote sensors, such as low resolution and light dependent video footage, as well as being a low cost and a potential long-term solution to traditional beach surveying techniques. This study aims to repurpose radar imagery, typically used for morphological monitoring (Bird et al., 2019), and provide a means of quantitatively assessing human beach user density over time using a trained classification model.

2 Methods and Data

2.1 Study area

The site chosen for beach user classification is Crosby Beach, Liverpool. This site was initially chosen for a commercial pilot study to study the viability of shore-based radar in tracking seabirds and disturbance events. The data used within this study was taken from the pilot study. A sub-section of the beach covering 0.9x1.5km between the hours of 09:00 and 14:00 on 28th February 2019 was analysed. This area included the Crosby beach promenade and a large groyne present along the foreshore. During the study period, a member of the team walked across the beach holding a GPS tracker, providing a track that can be used as a reference during the classification process.

2.2 Data processing

Radar image collection occurred approximately every 1.845 seconds, dependent on the rotation speed of the antennae. Over the course of the study period a total of 8458 images were collected. Each of the images underwent a bespoke processing algorithm outlined in Figure 1. The purpose of the gaussian smoothing method was to eradicate significant atmospheric noise from the imagery, caused by fog and

rainfall at the time. Gaussian thresholding then enabled image clutter reduction by filtering out the weaker signal returns, and leaving greater signal intensities, as these were likely to be target particles.

Figure 1. Data processing steps applied to each raw image

TrackPy, a Python tracking package, can be used over a series of images to detect particle movement over time. The Trackpy package uses a standard particle tracking algorithm to derive particle trajectories from a sequence of images. The algorithm returns a table featuring several particle attributes including the Euclidian locations of each tracked particle over time. Using bespoke functions, the speed, total distance (displacement), and linearity (line straightness) of each trajectory can be calculated. These mobility features were used in the subsequent classifications. The pre-processing of the imagery did not eradicate all of the clutter on the images, resulting in several ‘noisy’ trajectories surrounding the target trajectories which tend to be more linear with larger displacements (Figure 2a). Noisy, low displacement trajectories were removed through a filtering process. The resulting image contained target particle trajectories to be used for classification (Figure 2b).

Initially, a selection of images corresponding with the referenced GPS tracked walk were selected for particle tracking as this validated the processing algorithm and enabled the collection of real human trajectories.

Figure 2. (a) trackPy trajectory output over 832 frames displaying un-filtered trajectories and (b) distance filtered trajectories. Solid blue line represents the GPS tracked walk. Different particles are represented here by different colours.

2.3 Model performance

A series of classifiers were used to predict the class of each trajectory into ‘human’ and ‘non-human’ classes: Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR) and Random Forest (RF). A total of 1022 trajectories were manually labelled and used for training and testing the classifiers: 580 human trajectories and 442 non-human trajectories. Precision-recall scores were calculated following a k-fold cross validation with a 75/25% train/test split for each classification method, the results of which are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Precision-recall scores for each classification model across all folds.

Method	k-fold					mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>SVM</i>						
Precision	0.943	0.894	0.977	0.981	0.976	0.954
Recall	0.854	0.874	0.869	0.903	0.837	0.867
<i>Logistic</i>						
Precision	0.943	0.894	0.967	0.972	0.976	0.950
Recall	0.854	0.874	0.879	0.920	0.837	0.873
<i>Random forest</i>						
Precision	0.966	0.866	0.948	0.972	0.989	0.948
Recall	0.885	0.966	0.919	0.912	0.918	0.920

Figure 3. Confusion matrices for LR, RF and SVC classification models.

Though every model classified trajectories with a good degree of accuracy, RF outperformed other models in terms of predicting a greater proportion of trajectories correctly. Each model typically misclassified human particles as nonhuman at a higher rate than nonhuman misclassification, however these numbers remained low relative to accurate classifications (Figure 3).

2.4 Visualising beach user density

Following the model comparison, the feature extraction was applied to radar imagery of the beach between the hours of 10:00am – 11:00am, and 11:00am – 12:00pm, equating to a total of 3902 processed images. The trajectories present in these images were classified using the RF model trained on the training set data above. Figure 4 displays the relative densities of trajectories that have been classified as human during these periods. There are higher concentrations of beach user density further inland with sporadic albeit sparse patterns when looking seaward, particularly between 10:00am and 11:00am. A high beach user density in this area may be attributed to the nearby car park and a coastal path (Da Silva, 2002).

Figure 4. Hexmaps (left) and KDE (right) displaying the densities of classified human trajectories between the hours of 10:00-11:00 (top) and 11:00-12:00 (bottom)

The seaward increase in beach user density between the hours of 11:00-12:00 is almost synonymous with low tide (12:29pm), indicative that the tidal cycle may influence the spatio-temporal variations in beach user density. Regardless, the high prevalence of activity landwards suggests that, during the period of observation, human activity remains close to the public footpath and away from the shoreline.

3 Discussion and further work

The study has shown that it is possible to classify and capture the spatio-temporal patterns of human activity across a beach by repurposing radar imagery. Though this study only covered a short time span, there is a potential to monitor beach user density over longer time scales, given the continuous stream of data provided by radar systems. The identification of seasonal beach user hotspots can assist in economic, social and ecological management. For example, zone management and conservation initiatives preventing anthropogenic stressors (Weston et al., 2012; Soto et al., 2021) improving recreation and tourism (Alexandrakis, Manasakis, and Kampanis, 2015) and implementing public safety measures (Jiminez et al., 2007; Kane et al., 2021). Relationships between beach user density and changes in beach morphology can be observed efficiently through radar-derived topography, enabling intervention and resilience strategies to be deployed against anthropogenic impacts.

Though the RF model outperformed both SVC and LR in this instance, there is still a margin of error resulting in misclassifications. Error in this instance can be caused by complications with the tracking algorithm, for example the accidental tracking of noise and interference during the processing stage. Though the number of misclassifications remains low, there is room for improvement. Additionally, radar is unable to distinguish objects that are close together as separate entities, consequently displaying these objects as one large particle instead. It is therefore difficult to differentiate lone walkers from dog walkers and other groups using this method alone. Should these limitations be addressed, there is scope for multi-class classification models that are able to dissociate clusters and grant a granular classification for human and non-human beach users.

Further work for this project may include the adoption of this technique in a variety of conditions, including data collected under different weather conditions and perhaps different locations. There is a dearth of research in the spatio-temporal analysis of beach ecosystems and human interactions using radar data. This study hopes to be a forerunner in the field.

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5 Biographies

James Murphy is a third year Data CDT PhD student within the Geographic Data Science Lab at the University of Liverpool. Current research relates to building resilience in coastal cities and exploring the interactions between humans and coastal systems using remote sensing technologies.

Dani Arribas-Bel is a senior lecturer in Geographic Data Science at the University of Liverpool, and Deputy Programme Director for Urban Analytics and ESRC fellow at the Alan Turing Institute. Dani's research interests combine urban studies, computational methods and new forms of data. Dani currently serves as co-editor of the journal "Environment and Planning B - Urban Analytics & City Science" and the "Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series A - Statistics in Society", and chairs the Quantitative Methods Research Group of the Royal Geographical Society.

Professor Andy Plater is a coastal geomorphologist with a keen interest in reconstructing system response to changes in sea-level, sediment supply and extreme events. Andy's work focuses on

sedimentary archives of environmental change, and what can be determined from these archives in terms of environmental forcing, response and recovery, human impact and sediment provenance. My work also links to the application of modelling and monitoring to detect, characterize and predict coastal change for climate change adaptation.

Dr Cai Bird has worked in the coastal monitoring industry for nearly a decade. Following a PhD in Coastal monitoring specialising in the use of marine radar, he joined Marlan Maritime Technologies in 2015 who are now implementing a network of remote coast monitoring systems around the UK and worldwide.